

Interview on the development of SNOPI

Interviewer 1 Alexandre Freitas

Interviewer 2 Simone Costa

Interviewee: Murilo Scalser

The interview goal was to investigate, from the developer's point of view, whether the use of networked ontologies (particularly an extract of HCI-ON) helps the development of an AUI system. Aligned with this goal, we defined two main questions:

- 1. (Q1) How does the use of networked ontologies help in the development of an AUI system?**
- 2. (Q2) What are the benefits and difficulties of using networked ontologies in the development of an AUI system?**

In the interview questionnaire, Q1 and Q2 were detailed in more specific questions. They are listed below. For simplification, in the questions we adopted the term ontology referring to the HCI-ON extract (i.e., the networked ontologies) used to develop SNOPI.

- Q1.1. In which stages of SNOPI development (e.g., analysis, design, implementation) was the ontology useful? Why?
- Q1.2. In which stages the ontology was not helpful? Why?
- Q1.3. Do you consider that the ontology extract helped you to have a better understanding of the domain?
- Q2.1. What benefits have you noticed when using the ontology in SNOPI development?
- Q2.2. What difficulties have you faced when using the ontology in SNOPI development?
- Q2.3. Was this the first time you developed an ontology-based system? Briefly describe your experience.
- Q2.4. Would you use ontologies again to develop another system? Why?
- Q2.5. How was the SNOPI development process (e.g., you perform it based on your tacit knowledge and experience, you defined a process beforehand or did you follow an existing one, etc.)?